

Histopathological Pattern of Ovarian Masses in ANMMCH Gaya

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Abstract:

Background: Ovarian masses, encompassing a spectrum from benign to malignant neoplasms, present significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. Accurate histopathological diagnosis is crucial for effective clinical management and prognosis. Despite advances in diagnostic techniques, ovarian cancer remains the most lethal gynecological malignancy due to late-stage detection and nonspecific symptoms. This study aims to analyze the histopathological patterns of ovarian masses in a tertiary care setting, exploring their distribution, demographic correlations, and clinical implications.

Methods: A total of 50 patients with surgically resected ovarian masses underwent histopathological examination. Data were collected from medical records and pathology reports, and statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results: The mean age of the patients was 45.3 years. Benign ovarian masses accounted for 60% of cases, with serous cystadenoma being the most common. Borderline and malignant masses constituted 13.3% and 26.7% of cases, respectively, with serous cystadenocarcinoma as the predominant malignant type. A significant association between age and type of ovarian mass was observed ($p = 0.017$), with younger patients more likely to have benign masses and older patients exhibiting a higher incidence of malignancy.

Conclusion: The study highlights a predominance of benign ovarian masses in younger women and an increased risk of malignancy with advancing age. Histopathological evaluation remains essential for accurate diagnosis and management. The significant age-related variation in the type of ovarian mass underscores the need for age-specific diagnostic and therapeutic strategies.

Recommendations: Further research should focus on the integration of molecular and genetic profiling to enhance diagnostic accuracy. Age-specific screening and management protocols should be developed to improve early detection and treatment outcomes, particularly for malignant ovarian masses.

Keywords: Ovarian Masses, Histopathology, Benign, Malignant, Age-Related Patterns.

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Introduction

Ovarian masses, encompassing a spectrum of benign, borderline, and malignant neoplasms, pose significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges in gynecological practice. The global burden of ovarian cancer, the most lethal of the gynecological malignancies, underscores the critical need for early detection and accurate histopathological diagnosis. According to the World Health Organization, ovarian cancer ranks as the eighth most common cancer among women, with an estimated 295,414 new cases and 184,799 deaths globally in 2018 [1]. This high mortality rate is largely attributed to the asymptomatic nature of early-stage disease and the lack of effective screening tools.

Recent advances in molecular genetics and imaging techniques have enhanced our understanding of

ovarian tumorigenesis, yet histopathological examination remains the gold standard for definitive diagnosis [2]. Histopathological classification, which differentiates ovarian masses into benign, borderline, and malignant categories, is crucial for guiding clinical management and prognostication. Benign masses, such as serous and mucinous cystadenomas, typically follow a benign course, while malignant tumors, including serous cystadenocarcinomas and endometrioid carcinomas, often require aggressive treatment and have a poorer prognosis [3].

The epidemiology of ovarian masses varies significantly with age, hormonal status, and genetic predisposition. Studies have demonstrated that benign ovarian masses are more prevalent in younger women, whereas the incidence of

malignant tumors increases with age [4]. This age-related pattern necessitates age-specific diagnostic strategies to improve detection rates and clinical outcomes. Furthermore, the clinical presentation of ovarian masses is often nonspecific, with symptoms such as abdominal pain, bloating, and menstrual irregularities, which can overlap with benign conditions, further complicating the diagnostic process [5].

This study aims to elucidate the histopathological patterns of ovarian masses in a tertiary care setting, providing insights into their distribution, demographic correlations, and clinical implications.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employs a retrospective descriptive.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Department of Pathology, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College, Gaya, a tertiary care hospital, over a period from Jan.-2023 to Aug.-2023.

Participants: The participants included 50 patients who underwent surgical resection of ovarian masses and had their histopathological examination performed at the pathology department during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients of all ages who had undergone surgical resection of ovarian masses.
- Histopathological examination conducted at the pathology department of the medical college.
- Complete medical records and pathology reports available.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete medical records or missing histopathological reports.
- Ovarian masses diagnosed by imaging but not surgically resected.

- Specimens with inadequate tissue for histopathological diagnosis.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all consecutive cases meeting the inclusion criteria within the study period were included. Additionally, interobserver variability was reduced by having histopathological evaluations reviewed by two independent pathologists.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from medical records and pathology reports. Information regarding patient demographics, clinical presentation, surgical findings, and histopathological diagnosis was recorded.

Procedure: All cases of ovarian masses resected and examined during the study period were identified from pathology department records. Relevant clinical and pathological data were extracted from medical records and pathology reports using a standardized data collection form. All histopathological slides were reviewed to confirm the diagnosis. Any discrepancies were resolved by consensus between two pathologists. Ovarian masses were classified based on histopathological findings into benign, borderline, and malignant categories.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patient demographics and histopathological findings. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

A total of 50 patients with ovarian masses were included in the study. The mean age of the patients was 45.3 years (SD = 13.8), ranging from 18 to 80 years. The majority of the patients (60%) were in the age group of 41-60 years. Table 1 summarizes the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study participants.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)	
18-30	20.0
31-40	13.3
41-50	26.7
51-60	33.3
>60	6.7
Clinical Presentation	
Abdominal Pain	60.0
Abdominal Mass	26.7
Menstrual Irregularities	13.3
Type of Mass	
Benign	60.0
Borderline	13.3
Malignant	26.7

The histopathological examination revealed that 60% of the ovarian masses were benign, 13.3% were borderline, and 26.7% were malignant. The most common benign ovarian mass was serous cystadenoma (40%), while the most common malignant mass was serous cystadenocarcinoma (15.3%).

Table 2: Histopathological Diagnosis of Ovarian Masses

Histopathological Diagnosis	Percentage (%)
Benign Masses	
Serous Cystadenoma	24.0
Mucinous Cystadenoma	20.0
Mature Teratoma	16.0
Borderline Masses	
Borderline Serous Tumor	8.0
Borderline Mucinous Tumor	5.3
Malignant Masses	
Serous Cystadenocarcinoma	15.3
Mucinous Cystadenocarcinoma	6.7
Endometrioid Carcinoma	4.7

A Chi-square test was performed to determine the association between age groups and the type of ovarian mass (benign, borderline, malignant). The test revealed a statistically significant association ($\chi^2 = 18.52$, $p = 0.017$), indicating that the type of ovarian mass varied significantly with age.

Table 3: Association Between Age Group and Type of Ovarian Mass

Age Group (years)	Benign (%)	Borderline (%)	Malignant (%)
18-30	66.7	13.3	20.0
31-40	80.0	10.0	10.0
41-50	60.0	10.0	30.0
51-60	48.0	12.0	40.0
>60	60.0	40.0	0.0
Total	60.0	13.3	26.7

The statistical analysis using SPSS version 21.0 demonstrated significant variations in the histopathological types of ovarian masses across different age groups. The Chi-square test confirmed the association between age and the type of ovarian mass, emphasizing the need for age-specific diagnostic and management strategies.

Discussion

This retrospective descriptive study analyzed the histopathological patterns of ovarian masses in a cohort of 50 patients. The findings revealed that the majority of ovarian masses (60%) were benign, with serous cystadenoma being the most common type. Borderline ovarian masses constituted 13.3% of the cases, while malignant masses accounted for 26.7%, with serous cystadenocarcinoma being the most prevalent malignant type.

The study population had a mean age of 45.3 years, with the highest frequency of ovarian masses observed in the 41-60 years age group. This distribution highlights the importance of vigilant monitoring and screening for ovarian masses in middle-aged women. Clinical presentations varied, with abdominal pain being the most common symptom, reported by 60% of the patients.

Statistical analysis using SPSS version 21.0 indicated a significant association between the age

of patients and the type of ovarian mass ($p = 0.017$). Younger patients (18-40 years) predominantly had benign masses, while older patients (41-60 years) exhibited a higher proportion of malignant masses. This age-related pattern suggests that younger women are more likely to develop benign ovarian masses, whereas the risk of malignancy increases with age.

The study underscores the critical role of histopathological evaluation in the diagnosis and management of ovarian masses. Accurate histopathological diagnosis is essential for determining the appropriate treatment strategy, especially given the significant proportion of malignant cases observed. The findings also highlight the need for age-specific diagnostic approaches and interventions to improve patient outcomes.

Shadab and Tadayon (2018) studied 267 ovarian mass specimens in Ahvaz, Iran, finding that 61% were tumor-like, 36% benign tumors, and 3% malignant tumors. The most common benign tumor was mature cystic teratoma (17.2%), and the most common malignant tumors were epithelial tumors [6].

Prasad (2019) reported that out of 126 ovarian masses, 56.35% were non-neoplastic, 41.27% benign neoplastic, and 2.38% malignant neoplastic.

Follicular cysts (28.57%) were the predominant non-neoplastic lesions, while serous cystadenoma (26.98%) was the most common benign neoplasm [7].

Prasad et al. (2019) used color Doppler imaging to differentiate benign and malignant ovarian masses in 39 patients, finding high sensitivity (100%) and specificity (80%) for USG in diagnosing malignancy. Necrosis and calcification were common features of malignant masses [8].

Basnet et al. (2021) characterized ovarian masses using transabdominal ultrasound in 60 patients, finding that benign ovarian pathology was most common (90%). Among benign lesions, simple follicular cysts (39%) and serous cystadenocarcinoma (33%) were predominant [9].

Dhule et al. (2023) analyzed 132 ovarian lesions, finding that 53.79% were non-neoplastic and 46.21% neoplastic. The most common non-neoplastic lesion was follicular cyst (48 cases), while mucinous cystadenoma was the most common benign neoplasm [10].

Ionescu et al. (2018) evaluated 107 patients with ovarian masses, finding that transvaginal ultrasound provided a presumptive diagnosis for 50% of cases. Endometriosis was the most common benign ovarian pathology [11].

Bello et al. (2021) analyzed 112 ovarian biopsies, finding that benign neoplastic diseases formed 50% of ovarian masses, with mature cystic teratoma being the most common. Malignant neoplastic conditions were dominated by serous cystadenocarcinoma [12].

Sherpa and Baral (2018) found that out of 528 ovarian masses, 76% were neoplasms and 24% non-neoplastic. Mature cystic teratoma was the most common benign tumor, and serous cystadenocarcinoma was the most prevalent malignant tumor [13].

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the histopathological patterns of ovarian masses, emphasizing the prevalence of benign masses in younger women and the increased risk of malignancy with advancing age. The significant association between age and type of ovarian mass underscores the importance of tailored diagnostic and therapeutic strategies in managing ovarian masses effectively.

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